

FUZZY-BASED CLUSTERING OF WIRELESS SENSOR NETWORKS FOR MULTIPLE MOBILE AGENT ITINERARY PLANNING

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ABSTRACT

Mobile agent (MA) technology exhibits remarkable efficiency when integrated into Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs) for information processing tasks. MAs reduce network overhead by executing processing code locally on nodes and selectively transmitting significant data to designated remote sensor nodes, thereby enhancing data fusion and acquisition while minimizing energy depletion. However, in large-scale networks, relying on a single MA leads to significant delays, necessitating the use of multiple MAs to operate asynchronously and minimize latency. The challenge lies in effectively grouping nodes to ensure MAs reach their intended destinations.

To address this challenge, this paper introduces a novel approach, the Adaptive FCM Clustering Algorithm (AFCM), a fuzzy-based clustering algorithm designed for addressing network partitioning challenges in Multiple Mobile Agent Itinerary Planning (MIP). A systematic analysis of the existing literature examines various MIP algorithms, emphasizing their strengths and uncovering potential research gaps. AFCM is specifically developed to create disjoint and load-balanced partitions tailored for multi-mobile agent itinerary planning. A Methodical analysis with three traditional clustering algorithms is conducted. The correctness of the Adaptive Fuzzy C-Means (AFCM) algorithm is demonstrated through a detailed manual application on a wireless network comprising 15 nodes.

KEYWORDS

Clustering, Itinerary planning, Mobile agent, Routing, Wireless sensor networks.

1. INTRODUCTION

Mobile agents are software agents capable of autonomously migrating with their processing code and data state to perform specified data processing tasks for remote users [1], [2]. They can resume execution even after disconnection and process data at designated nodes. This flexibility allows them to efficiently utilize network bandwidth, conserve energy, and minimize latency [3], [4], [5], [6]. However, the deployment of mobile agents is only necessary when dealing with substantial amounts of data transmission. In traditional Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs), deploying numerous sensor nodes in close proximity often leads to redundant sensed data. Transmitting this redundant data individually consumes significant energy and bandwidth [7], [8], [9], [10], [11]. In contrast, mobile agents migrate to each node, process and accumulate reduced data in their payload, and perform aggregation with previously accumulated and newly retrieved data [12], [13], [14]. By delivering only processed and aggregated information to the intended node, mobile agents enable accurate decision-making based on significant information.

Despite its numerous benefits, mobile agent (MA) technology also presents challenges, with mobile agent routing being a prominent issue [15], [16], [17], [18]. Routing mobile agents involves determining their optimal itinerary, which includes the sequence of migration and the group of nodes to be visited. The itinerary must be carefully planned to ensure that the collaborative system performs better than the traditional system. The problem is divided into three steps to address this:

- dividing the network into appropriate and disjoint clusters
- creating a group of source nodes to be visited within a single itinerary
- deciding the visiting order for completing their tasks.

This research paper addresses the initial step of the stated problem, which involves partitioning the network into disjoint domains. To address this challenge, the study introduces an algorithm that partitions a Wireless Sensor network into distinct, non-overlapping domains, thereby improving the efficiency of the mobile agent system.

The proposed algorithm introduces a novel approach for autonomously determining the cardinality for network segmentation. It dynamically selects the optimal number of domains (clusters) and effectively partitions the network into non-overlapping, disjoint segments. Additionally, the algorithm adeptly resolves the challenge of assigning nodes equidistant from two centroids to the correct domain, ensuring precise network segmentation.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

This research investigates the use of the mobile agent paradigm for Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs) in communicating data. The mobile agent paradigm offers advantages such as efficient resource utilization, reduced network bandwidth usage, improved scalability, and offline stability. However, the effective operation of mobile agents requires careful planning of their migration path to avoid energy consumption and delays. Path determination can be achieved through static or dynamic itinerary planning. Static planning is suitable for known node sequences in physical data monitoring, while dynamic planning is used for target tracking with mobile and evolving targets. Table 1 presents a summary of the literature reviewed in this study, outlining the main findings and methodologies explored.

Table 1: Clustering Techniques in Wireless Sensor Networks: A Review of Relevant Studies

Algorithms with sources	Strategy used	Research gap and strength of the proposed algorithm	Description of the algorithm
GIGM-MIP [19], Aloui et al. [20], SMIP [21], Daramola et al. [22]	k-means and x-means	The challenge is to identify k value	Consider the proximity of source nodes to associate respective CH(Cluster Head).
MST-MIP [3], TBID [12], MINDS [23], NOID [24], ILS [25], Disjoint MIP [26], CBID [27], SNOID [28]	Tree-structured	Consume more energy and take a long time to traverse as MA has to migrate each node twice by following reverse mapping	Single MA is dedicated to each stemmed branch
CSA-MIP [4], Kuila et al. [29], Wu et al. [30], Rajagopalan et al. [31], GA-MIP [32]	GA based	Not effective for time-critical applications	Select the sequence of source nodes for the gene array randomly.
CL-MIP [33], EMIP [34], OM-MIP [35], MAEF [36]	VCL based	Centers are chosen on density base	Partitions are in circular sector zones
SGMIP [35], DSGMIP [37], Bendjima et al. [38]	Directionality based	Difficult to identify angle θ	Distribute sensor nodes in concentric zones, originating with VCL lines
AG-MIP [39], SLMADA [40]	Angle based	Outperforms when almost nodes are in the same direction. Still an issue to determine angle θ	Partitions the network into concentric sector zones, using two beelines with angle θ
BM-FPA [41], MFGSA [42]	Evolutionary technique	Good enough, but due to the collaboration of a number of techniques, it becomes very complex	The results obtained from fuzzy-based membership are carefully incorporated into a PSO-based clustering technique, which is iteratively executed to determine the global optimal results.
RA-MDP [43]	k-medoids	Difficult to identify k value	CHs are chosen using angle gap-based strategy

The review of literature, detailed in Table 1, highlights different algorithms employed for network partitioning in multiple Mobile Agent Itinerary Planning (MIP), each with its unique advantages and limitations. Building on these observations, this study presents a new approach with the Adaptive FCM Clustering Algorithm, designed to generate disjoint and balanced partitions tailored for multi-mobile agent itinerary planning.

This research paper addresses the challenges of clustering in context to Mobile Agent routing in Wireless Sensor Networks, specifically focusing on issues related to overlapping and load balancing. The paper introduces the proposed AFCM algorithm and compares it with three traditional clustering algorithms. To validate the algorithm, a manual demonstration is provided using a 15-node wireless network. Additionally, the algorithm was implemented in Python to further verify its accuracy, and the results supported its correctness. The conclusions and findings of these investigations are discussed in the concluding section of the paper.

3. ENHANCING MULTI-MOBILE AGENT ITINERARY PLANNING: INTRODUCING AN ADAPTIVE FUZZY C-MEANS ALGORITHM FOR NETWORK CLUSTERING

After conducting a review of existing literature on multi-mobile agent itinerary planning (MIP), it was observed that network clustering plays a crucial role in achieving efficient MIP. Various algorithms, including k-means, x-means, tree-based, genetic algorithm-based, center location-based, and directional-based approaches, have been proposed to partition the network and optimize MIP.

The main drawback of the k-means clustering algorithm is its requirement to specify the number of clusters beforehand. Variants such as x-means and Fuzzy c-Means (FCM) are built upon the k-means framework. In x-means clustering, an initial minimum number of centroids is assumed, and clusters are subsequently adjusted to achieve optimal configuration. FCM algorithms, on the other hand, start with a fixed number of clusters and iteratively update centroids while assigning data points to clusters based on membership values to optimize results. Although x-means, k-means, and FCM share some characteristics, FCM is distinguished as a prominent soft clustering method, allowing data points to belong to multiple clusters simultaneously according to their membership degrees.

However, Fuzzy c-Means (FCM) encounters challenges when a sensor node has equal membership values for multiple destination itineraries, potentially resulting in imbalanced domains within multi-mobile agent itinerary planning (MIP) systems. To address this issue, this paper proposes a revised version of the FCM algorithm, termed Adaptive Fuzzy C-Means (AFCM), designed to improve network clustering in MIP applications.

The AFCM algorithm addresses the issue of imbalanced domains by associating each sensor node with the Domain Initial (DI) that has the lower expected load. This method helps to balance the domains, thereby enhancing the efficiency of multi-mobile agent itinerary planning (MIP) systems. The research will assess the AFCM algorithm's capability to manage cases where sensor nodes have equal membership values for multiple DIs and evaluate its effectiveness in creating balanced domains.

By overcoming the limitations of existing clustering algorithms, particularly Fuzzy C-Means (FCM), the proposed study aims to improve the performance and efficacy of MIP systems. The evaluation of the AFCM algorithm's performance in network clustering for MIP will contribute to the advancement of more effective itinerary planning techniques in multi-agent systems.

3.1. Distinguishing Clustering Algorithms: Exploring AFCM's Motivation and Uncovering Algorithmic Differentiations

Table 2 offers a detailed comparison of the k-means, x-means, and fuzzy c-means clustering algorithms. This analysis aims to clarify the reasons for introducing the Advanced Fuzzy C-Means (AFCM) algorithm. By highlighting the unique characteristics and limitations of each algorithm, the table helps to identify the specific strengths and weaknesses that drive the development of AFCM as a novel approach in clustering techniques.

Table 2: Comparison between k-means, x-means, and fuzzy c-means clustering algorithms

Aspect	k-means	x-means	fuzzy c-means
Determining the Number of Clusters	Requires specifying the number of clusters (k) in advance.	Begins with initial centroids and adjusts the number of clusters dynamically.	Requires specifying the number of clusters ahead of time.
Centroid Computation	Computes centroids as the mean of data points in each cluster.	Identifies optimal sub-clusters by decomposing clusters, leading to new centroids.	Iteratively updates centroids based on the weighted values of data points.
Membership Assignment	Assigns data points to the nearest centroid, resulting in hard assignments.	Uses a likelihood-based criterion for probabilistic assignment to sub-clusters.	Assigns membership values indicating the degree of belonging to each cluster.
Handling Overlapping and Noise	Ineffective at handling overlapping or noisy data.	Manages overlapping clusters to some extent by decomposing them into sub-clusters.	Effectively manages overlapping and noisy data.
Flexibility and Adaptability	Fixed number of clusters; lacks adaptability.	Flexible, as it dynamically determines the number of clusters during clustering.	Flexible in both the number of clusters and the degree of membership.
Performance	Performs well with well-separated and spherical clusters.	Offers enhanced performance by automatically determining the optimal number of clusters.	Robust performance on datasets with overlapping or non-spherical clusters.
Ease of Mobile Agent Itinerary Planning	Less suitable due to fixed cluster number and inability to handle overlapping.	More suitable as it adjusts cluster numbers dynamically, aiding itinerary planning.	Highly suitable due to its flexibility in handling overlapping clusters and varying degrees of membership.

This table offers a succinct overview of the primary distinctions among the algorithms. It is important to note that their performance can vary based on the particular dataset and the nature of the clustering task.

3.1.1. Description of the Adaptive Fuzzy C-Means (AFCM) Clustering Algorithm for Sensor Networks

This section provides a detailed, point-by-point description of the Adaptive Fuzzy C-Means (AFCM) Clustering Algorithm, tailored for use in Sensor Networks.

1. AFCM approach: The Adaptive Fuzzy C-Means (AFCM) Clustering Algorithm for Sensor Networks operates without the need to specify the number of clusters (k) in advance.

2. Selection of processing node (PE): AFCM selects a centralized processing node (PE) within the network.
3. Determining k: The number of Sensor Nodes (SNs) in the vicinity of the PE becomes the value of k. These SNs are referred to as domain initials (DI).
4. Assignment of Remaining Sensor Nodes (SNs): The remaining sensor nodes are allocated to the domain initials (DI_i) within the set DI. For each remaining sensor node, the membership value (μ_i, j) is computed relative to each domain initial (DI_i) in its vicinity.
5. Sum of membership values: The sum of membership values ($\sum \mu_i, j$) of each remaining SN with respect to each DI_i is calculated in advance.
6. Calculation of Sum of membership values: The total sum of membership values ($\sum \mu_i, j$) for each remaining sensor node (SN) with respect to each domain initial (DI_i) is computed beforehand.
7. Assignment to Domain Initials (DI_i): Each sensor node is allocated to the domain initial (DI_i) that has the highest membership value. After each assignment, the sum of membership values ($\sum \mu_i, j$) is recalculated.
8. Finalizing Assignments: The assignment process continues until all sensor nodes in the network are allocated to a designated domain initial (DI_i). For nodes that have identical membership values across multiple DI_s, they are assigned to the DI_i with the lowest total sum of membership values ($\sum \mu_i, j$).
9. Threshold Comparison: The updated sum of membership values ($\sum \mu_i, j$) is compared against a predefined threshold, which represents the minimum value required for deploying a single Mobile Agent (MA). Domain initials (DI_i) with $\sum \mu_i, j$ values falling below this threshold are excluded from further consideration.
10. Domain Reduction: To minimize the number of domain initials (DI_s) or DI_i, existing domain initials and their assigned nodes are consolidated. This merging process facilitates the creation of non-overlapping, load-balanced domains, ensuring a more efficient distribution of sensor nodes.

3.1.2. Distinctive Features of the Adaptive Fuzzy C-Means (AFCM) Algorithm in Comparison to k-means, x-Means, and Fuzzy c-Means (FCM)

1. Requirement for Cluster Number Specification:
 - k-means: Requires an explicit specification of the number of clusters prior to execution, which can limit its adaptability to diverse data distributions.
 - x-Means: Addresses the limitation of fixed cluster numbers by iteratively adjusting and refining the number of centroids based on data characteristics.
 - Fuzzy c-Means (FCM): Does not necessitate a fixed number of clusters from the outset, but still relies on initial estimates that can influence clustering outcomes.
 - Adaptive Fuzzy c-Means (AFCM): Advances beyond these methods by determining the number of clusters dynamically, based on the proximity of nodes to a central processing node, thus eliminating the need for pre-specified cluster numbers.
2. Cluster Initialization:
 - k-means: Initializes clusters either randomly or through a predefined method, which may not always align with the data distribution.
 - x-Means: Starts with an initial cluster configuration and iteratively adjusts the cluster count to enhance data fit.

- Fuzzy c-Means (FCM): Initiates with centroids and iteratively refines them based on membership values, though initial cluster estimates still play a role.
- AFCM: Uniquely establishes initial clusters (domain initials) using nodes in proximity to the processing node, thus aligning initial clusters more closely with local data characteristics.

3. Cluster Assignment Method:

- k-means: Assigns nodes to the nearest centroid, potentially leading to imbalanced clusters if the initial number of clusters is suboptimal.
- x-Means: Iteratively refines cluster assignments as the number of clusters is adjusted, improving alignment with data distribution.
- Fuzzy c-Means (FCM): Utilizes fuzzy membership values to assign nodes to clusters, allowing for partial membership but not necessarily optimizing cluster count.
- AFCM: Assigns nodes to clusters based on the highest membership value in an iterative manner, ensuring effective and balanced allocation of all nodes.

4. Clustering Optimization:

- k-means: Does not perform dynamic optimization of cluster numbers after initialization, which can lead to inefficiencies if the fixed number of clusters is not ideal.
- x-Means: Enhances clustering by iteratively optimizing the number of clusters, adapting based on data fit.
- Fuzzy c-Means (FCM): Focuses on centroid optimization according to membership values but does not dynamically adjust the number of clusters.
- AFCM: Provides a sophisticated optimization approach by calculating the sum of membership values in advance. It discards clusters with low membership sums and redistributes nodes to remaining clusters, resulting in non-overlapping and load-balanced domains.

5. Handling Low Membership Clusters:

- k-means: Fixed clusters remain unchanged regardless of membership distribution, which may not address low membership issues.
- x-Means: Adapts the number of clusters based on data fit but does not specifically address low membership clusters.
- Fuzzy c-Means (FCM): Concentrates on refining centroid positions without dynamically adjusting or eliminating low membership clusters.
- AFCM: Actively manages clusters with low membership sums by eliminating them and reassigning their nodes, thereby optimizing clustering efficiency and balance.

In summary, the AFCM algorithm offers significant improvements over k-means, x-Means, and FCM by dynamically determining the number of clusters based on node proximity, optimizing cluster assignments, and achieving more balanced and efficient clustering in sensor networks.

Table 3 gives a comprehensive comparison that includes all aspects for k-means, x-Means, Fuzzy c-Means (FCM), and Adaptive Fuzzy c-Means (AFCM)

Table 3: Comprehensive Comparison of k-means, x-Means, Fuzzy c-Means (FCM), and Adaptive Fuzzy c-Means (AFCM): Key Aspects and Distinctive Features

Aspect	k-means	x-Means	Fuzzy c-Means (FCM)	Adaptive Fuzzy c-Means (AFCM)
Pre-determined Number of Clusters	Requires pre-determination of the number of clusters (k).	Adjusts the number of clusters iteratively, refining k based on data distribution.	Does not require a fixed number of clusters but may need initial estimates.	Does not require pre-determined number of clusters; determines dynamically based on node proximity.
Dynamic Adjustment of Clusters	No dynamic adjustment; clusters are fixed after initialization.	Dynamically adjusts the number of clusters by evaluating and splitting clusters.	Adjusts cluster centroids based on membership values but not the number of clusters.	Dynamically adjusts the number of clusters based on nodes' proximity to the processing node.
Cluster Initialization	Clusters are initialized randomly or using a predefined method.	Initializes clusters and then iterates to refine the number based on fit.	Initializes centroids and adjusts iteratively based on membership values.	Initial clusters are formed from nodes within the processing node's vicinity.
Cluster Assignment	Nodes are assigned to the nearest cluster centroid.	Nodes are assigned iteratively as clusters are refined.	Nodes are assigned based on fuzzy membership values to each cluster.	Nodes are assigned to clusters based on highest membership value iteratively.
Optimization	No optimization of cluster count; fixed after initialization.	Optimizes cluster count iteratively, adding or removing clusters as needed.	Optimizes cluster centroids based on membership values but does not adjust cluster count dynamically.	Optimizes clustering by calculating membership values and dropping clusters below a threshold.
Cluster Efficiency	May result in imbalanced clusters if the number of clusters is not optimal.	Improves cluster balance by dynamically adjusting cluster count.	Handles overlapping data but may not balance clusters as dynamically.	Achieves non-overlapping, load-balanced clusters by dynamically adjusting and optimizing assignments.
Handling of Low Membership Clusters	Not applicable; clusters are fixed.	Not specifically addressed; adjusts cluster count based on data fit.	Does not dynamically drop clusters; focuses on centroid adjustments.	Drops clusters with low membership sums and reassigns nodes to existing clusters to balance load.

3.1.3. Comparative Analysis of Fuzzy c-Means (FCM) and Adaptive Fuzzy c-Means (AFCM) Algorithms: Advancements, Adaptability, and Efficiency

Comparing the Fuzzy c-Means (FCM) and Adaptive Fuzzy c-Means (AFCM) algorithms is crucial for understanding their respective strengths and advancements in clustering research. While FCM requires pre-determined cluster numbers and operates with static cluster adjustments, AFCM introduces dynamic cluster determination based on node proximity, significantly enhancing its adaptability to varying data distributions. This dynamic approach allows AFCM to optimize clustering through iterative membership calculations and cluster reduction, leading to

more balanced and efficient clustering outcomes compared to FCM. Additionally, evaluating these algorithms helps identify their suitability for different applications, particularly in scenarios requiring dynamic adjustments and efficient resource management. Overall, this comparison highlights AFCM's practical advantages in handling dynamic and resource-sensitive clustering tasks more effectively than FCM.

Table 4 offers a concise yet thorough comparison between the Fuzzy c-Means (FCM) and Adaptive Fuzzy c-Means (AFCM) algorithms, highlighting their key differences and demonstrating the advantages of AFCM over FCM.

Table 4: Distinctions between Fuzzy C-Means (FCM) and Adaptive Fuzzy C-Means (AFCM) algorithms

Distinction Issues	Fuzzy c-Means (FCM)	Adaptive Fuzzy c-Means (AFCM)
Approach	Standard FCM algorithm	Adaptive FCM algorithm
Pre-determined number of clusters (k)	Required	Not required
Selection of processing node (PE)	Not applicable	Centralized processing node
Determining k	Not applicable	Number of Sensor Nodes (SNs) in the vicinity of the PE
Assigning remaining SNs	Based on membership values	Based on membership values within the vicinity of each domain initial (DI _i)
Sum of membership values	Not calculated in advance	Calculated in advance
Assignment to DI	Maximum membership value	Maximum membership value with consideration of the lowest sum of membership values ($\sum \mu_{i,j}$)
Assignment completion	Based on membership values	Based on membership values and $\sum \mu_{i,j}$ values
Comparing with threshold value	Not applicable	Comparison of updated $\sum \mu_{i,j}$ values with a threshold value
Reducing domains	Not applicable	Merging domain initials and assigned nodes for load-balanced domains

These distinctions highlight the key differences between the FCM and AFCM algorithms, emphasizing the adaptive nature of AFCM, which does not require pre-determining the number of clusters (k) and incorporates additional steps for processing node selection, assignment completion, and domain reduction to achieve load-balanced domains in sensor networks.

4. ADAPTIVE FUZZY-BASED CLUSTERING ALGORITHM (AFCM): A COMPREHENSIVE DESCRIPTION

The proposed algorithm addresses critical challenges in clustering, such as load balancing and cluster overlapping. Unlike traditional set theories, fuzzy-based partitioning captures the degree of belongingness of each sensor node (SN) to the network. Equation 1 illustrates that the degree of membership (μ) represents the similarity between nodes. Sensor nodes are grouped based on the domain initial (DI) with the highest $\mu_{i,j}$ value, where $\mu_{i,j} \in [0, 1]$. Nodes near the center have higher μ values, while those near the boundary have lower μ values. The algorithm utilizes membership functions to map distances to degrees of membership ($\mu_{i,j}$).

4.1. Objective and Methodology: Associating Source Nodes with Domain Initials

In a collaborative system, the processing element (PE) assigns mobile agents (MAs) to specific starting points known as domain initials (DIs), where DI_{*l*} represents the candidate's starting point for an MA's journey. The set DI consists of source nodes that are within the transmission range of the PE.

The objective of the proposed algorithm is to associate source nodes with their corresponding DIs. This association ensures that for every source node *i* in the set SN ($\forall i \in N$), there exists a DI_{*j*} in the set DI such that *i* is within the transmission range of *j* i.e. j_{range} . Any source nodes that are not directly associated with a DI are placed in the set NDA (not directly associated). The algorithm employs fuzzy-based clustering to determine the degree of association $\mu_{i,j}$, calculated using equation 2. The clustering process follows the constraints specified in equations 3 and 4, ensuring exhaustive partitioning and disjointness among the DIs.

$$\mu_{i,j} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } i = j \\ \frac{d_{i,j}^{-2}}{\sum_{l=1}^{|DI|} d_{l,j}^{-2}} & \text{Otherwise} \end{cases} \quad \forall i \in N, l \neq j \quad (1)$$

$$\mu_{i,j} = \frac{d_{i,j}^{-2}}{\sum_{l=1}^{|DI|} d_{l,j}^{-2}} \quad (2)$$

Here,

|DI| is the cardinality of the set containing source nodes within the vicinity of the processing element (PE).

'*m*' The balancing exponent that determines the level of crispness or fuzziness in the clustering process.

- The value of '*m*' can be adjusted adaptively.
- A lower value of '*m*' results in sharper boundaries between clusters, making them more distinct.
- Conversely, a higher value of '*m*' leads to softer boundaries between clusters, allowing for more overlap and uncertainty.

Equation 3 ensures that the total degree of association between each source node and the domain initials within its vicinity always adds up to one. This constraint guarantees the disjunction of any two domains, meaning that no source node is connected to more than one domain initial.

$$\sum_{i=1}^{|DI|} \mu_{i,j} = 1, \forall j \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, n\} \quad (3)$$

In Equation 4, it is ensured that the sum of the degree of membership values of each source node which comes under its vicinity (i_{range}) with respect to each domain initial is always non-zero. This constraint guarantees that each domain initial has an expected assigned load from each source node in the network, preventing any null assignments.

$$\sum_{i=1}^n \mu_{i,j} > 0, \forall j \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, |DI|\}, \exists j : d(i, j) \leq i_{range} \quad (4)$$

In this section, a concise description of the proposed partitioning algorithm for wireless sensor networks is provided. Once the domain initials (DIs) have been established, the subsequent step involves allocating the remaining nodes to their corresponding domain initials (DIi).

4.2. Problem Statement

Clustering of the wireless sensor network into disjoint and equally loaded appropriate number of domains.

Given:

1. $SN = \{SN \in i = 1, 2, \dots, n\}$ – Documented set of n sensor nodes.
2. $D = \{d_{ij}, \text{ where, } i \in 1 \text{ to } n; j \in 1 \text{ to } n; i \neq j\}$ – Given by Table 2: Spatial distance of each sensor node in illustrated wireless sensor network, where d_{ij} is the Euclidean distance, described as the whole number.
3. The transmission range of each sensor node is taken as 5.

To find out:

Exhaustive partition of a set of source nodes (SN) into c number of domains.

Steps for proposed AFCM algorithm

1. *Given: Set of n number of sensor nodes. $SN = \{1, 2, 3, \dots, n\}$;*
2. $N = \{SN - x: x \text{ is any centrally located node in the network}\}$; /*set of nodes that are to be associated with the domains. This set contains all sensor nodes except the processing element.
3. *Set Level=0; Choose $L_{level} = \{i: d(PE, i) \leq PE_{range}\}$; /* MA will be dispatched by PE by choosing the nodes which directly come under PE's vicinity. These nodes are termed domain initials.*
4. *Update $N_{level} = \{N - L_{level}\}$;*
5. *Determine subsets of L_{level} , $DI = \{\exists j : d(i, j) \leq j_{range} : \forall i \in N_{level}, \forall j \in L_{level}\}$; /* Set of domain initials to which source node may be connected.*
6. $NDA = \{\exists i \in N_{level} : d(i, j) > j_{range}, \forall j \in L_{level}\}$; /* Set of nodes $i \in N$, which are not directly connected to L_{level} .
If $(NDA \neq \emptyset)$ then
 $N_{level} = N_{level} - NDA$;
7. *Find $\mu_{i,j} = \frac{d_{i,j}^{\frac{-2}{m-1}}}{\sum_{l=1}^{|DI|} d_{i,l}^{\frac{-2}{m-1}}}$, $\forall i \in N_{level}$ w.r.t. each DI such that $d(i, j) \leq i_{range} \forall i \in N_{level}, \forall j \in L_{level}$;*
8. *Calculate the estimated load of each DI by adding μ values of each DI w.r.t. nodes that come under their vicinity;*
9. *Associate the nodes with the DI_i*
10. *If $(NDA \neq \emptyset)$ then*
 - i) $L_{level} = N_{level}$,
 - ii) $Level = Level + 1$,
 - iii) $N_{level} = NDA$,
 - iv) *Go to step 5 and repeat until $NDA = \emptyset$;*
11. *Check if there is any domain having data to be carried by the mobile agent less than the MA's threshold value then less loaded domain needs to be dropped out by following step 11 else go to step 13;*

12. Identify each node of this domain (to be dropped out) with their corresponding L_{level} and assign identified nodes to their respective same level by considering membership values;
13. Stop;

In some domains, the amount of data that needs to be carried by the Mobile Agent (MA) associated with the domain's nodes may be less than the MA's threshold value. The threshold value represents the minimum data quantity for which a dedicated MA should be deployed. In such cases, these domains should be excluded or dropped out. Consequently, all relevant nodes will be associated with their respective domain, denoted by $j \in L_i$, where the membership degree (μ) is maximum. Similarly, the remaining nodes that were previously associated with the dropped domain (j) should be connected to the remaining domains (j).

4.3. Evaluating Efficiency of Fuzzy-Based Clustering Algorithm for Wireless Sensor Network Partitioning: An Illustrative Example

In Figure 1, a specific instance of a wireless sensor network comprising 15 nodes is depicted. The figure also demonstrates the spatial separation between nodes within the network.

Figure 1. Representation of a Wireless Sensor Network with 15 Nodes

The Fuzzy C-means (FCM) clustering algorithm, initially applied to wired networks as detailed in [44], is here re-examined in the context of wireless sensor networks (WSNs) using the same illustrative network. This study shifts focus to explore fuzzy-based clustering in WSNs, as presented in Table 5, which outlines the range matrix for the discussed network. The objective is to demonstrate the algorithm's effectiveness in partitioning both wired and wireless networks while ensuring that clusters maintain non-overlapping domains. The research highlights the significant differences between clustering wired and wireless networks due to their distinct characteristics: wired networks have fixed, stable topologies that optimize static connections, whereas WSNs feature dynamic, irregular topologies with mobile nodes, necessitating adaptable clustering strategies to address issues such as energy constraints and communication variability. By comparing clustering outcomes in WSNs with those from wired networks, this study emphasizes the need for tailored approaches that effectively manage the unique challenges of each network type.

The distinction between applying the proposed clustering algorithm to wired versus wireless networks lies in how proximity is considered. In wireless networks, clusters are formed based on the wireless range between the processing elements and the centroids of the nodes selected for clustering. This approach accounts for the variable communication range and signal strength

inherent to wireless environments. In contrast, in wired networks, clustering is based on the physical proximity of nodes to each other rather than their proximity to a centroid. This reflects the fixed and stable nature of wired connections, where mutual proximity is the primary factor in cluster formation. The application of the proposed algorithm is illustrated as follows:

Table 5: Spatial distance of each sensor node in wireless sensor network[39]

$d_{i,j}$	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
1	0	3	6	3	2	8	8	6	8	11	11	12	12	10	12
2	3	0	3	2	3	7	8	6	8	12	12	12	12	10	12
3	6	3	0	3	6	4	6	6	7	10	10	10	10	8	10
4	3	2	3	0	3	5	6	4	6	10	10	10	9	8	10
5	2	3	6	3	0	8	6	4	6	10	10	10	10	8	10
6	8	7	4	5	8	0	5	8	9	5	5	5	7	9	11
7	8	8	6	6	6	5	0	3	4	6	4	4	4	4	6
8	6	6	6	4	4	8	3	0	2	9	7	6	6	4	6
9	8	8	7	6	6	9	4	2	0	10	8	6	4	2	4
10	11	12	1	0	10	10	5	6	9	1	0	2	4	8	10
11	11	12	1	0	10	10	5	4	7	8	2	0	2	6	8
12	12	12	1	0	10	10	5	4	6	6	4	2	0	4	6
13	12	12	1	0	9	10	7	4	6	4	8	6	4	0	2
14	10	10	8	8	8	9	4	4	2	10	8	6	2	0	2
15	12	12	1	0	10	10	11	6	6	4	12	10	8	4	2

Node 8, selected as the Processing Node (PE) due to its central location, serves as the basis for the proposed fuzzy-based clustering algorithm. With the chosen PE, nodes 4, 5, 7, 9, and 14 will be grouped together as elements of the set DI. Table 6 provides a list of domains to which each source node may be connected. However, node 10 does not have any domain (DI_i) within its transmission range. Therefore, node 10 will be categorized as a member of the set NDA (Not Directly Associated) in this context. Table 7 presents the degree of membership (belongingness) of each source node (SN_i) to its corresponding Domain Initial (DI).

Table6: Set of domain initials to which node may be connected

Node SN _i	Expected domain initials (DI) to which SN _i node may be connected
1	{4, 5}
2	{4, 5}
3	{4}
6	{4, 7}
10	{}
11	{7}
12	{7}
13	{7, 9, 14}
15	{9, 14}

Table 7: Membership values (μ) of each sensor node for the current set of domain initials

SN_i	Membership value (μ) with DI_4	Membership value (μ) with DI_5	Membership value (μ) with DI_7	Membership value (μ) with DI_9	Membership value (μ) with DI_{14}
1	$2/5 = 0.4$	$3/5 = 0.6$	--	--	--
2	$3/5 = 0.6$	$2/5 = 0.4$	--	--	--
3	1	--	--	--	--
6	$1/2 = 0.5$	--	$1/2 = 0.5$	--	--
10	--	--	--	--	--
11	--	--	1	--	--
12	--	--	1	--	--
13	--	--	$1/4 = 0.25$	$1/4 = 0.25$	$1/2 = 0.5$
15	--	--	--	$1/3 = 0.333$	$2/3 = 0.666$

In this scenario, the expected assigned load for each domain initial can be calculated by summing the membership values of each domain initial with respect to each sensor node. For the given example, the expected assigned load for domain initials 4, 5, 7, 9, and 14 are 2.5, 1, 2.75, 0.583, and 1.166, respectively.

Table 8: Association of succeeding sensor nodes to their respective domain initial

Sensor nodes with feasible DIs	DI_4 (carried load (2.5), set of related nodes)	DI_5 (carried load (1), set of related nodes)	DI_7 (carried load (2.75), set of related nodes)	DI_9 (carried load (0.583), set of related nodes)	DI_{14} (carried load (1.166), set of related nodes)
3	2.5, {3}	1, { }	2.75, { }	0.583, { }	1.166, { }
11	2.5, {3}	1, { }	2.75, { 11, 12}	0.583, { }	1.166, { }
12	2.5, {3}	1, { }	2.75, { 11, 12}	0.583, { }	1.166, { }
1	1.9, {3}	1, {1}	2.75, { 11, 12}	0.583, { }	1.166, { }
2	1.9, {2, 3}	0.6, {1}	2.75, { 11, 12}	0.583, { }	1.166, { }
6	1.9, {2, 3, 6}	0.6, {1}	2.25, { 11, 12}	0.583, { }	1.166, { }
15	1.9, {2, 3, 6}	0.6, {1}	2.25, {11, 12}	0.25, { }	1.166, {15}
13	1.9, {2, 3, 6}	0.6, {1}	2, {11, 12}	0	1.166, {13, 15}
3	2.5, {3}	1, { }	2.75, { }	0.583, { }	1.166, { }

Table 8 presents the nodes in ascending order of the cardinality of set DI (as shown in Table 6), ensuring that nodes with smaller cardinality sets are associated first. In the assignment process, each node is associated with the DI_i that has the highest membership value, as indicated in Table 7. However, if multiple DI_i have the same membership value for a node, the node is connected to the DI_i with the lower assigned load. This approach ensures that all nodes within the vicinity of DI_i are appropriately associated.

In contrast, the set NDA contains one element, node 10, which needs to be connected to the source nodes that are already linked to DI in the previous iteration. In this iteration, the elements of set DI are replaced by the elements of set N, i.e., 1, 2, 3, 6, 11, 12, 13, and 15, while the elements of set N are replaced by the element of set NDA, which is 10. Table 9 displays the degree of belongingness of node 10 with respect to the new set DI.

 Table 9: Membership values (μ) of the set NDA for the new set DI

SN_i	μ w.r.t. DI_1	μ w.r.t. DI_2	μ w.r.t. DI_3	μ w.r.t. DI_6	μ w.r.t. DI_{11}	μ w.r.t. DI_{12}	μ w.r.t. DI_{13}	μ w.r.t. DI_{15}
10	--	--	--	0.211	0.526	0.263	--	--

Since node 10 comes under the vicinity of 6, 11, and 12 nodes directly. Degree of belongingness

of the node w.r.t. the relatively new data sets 6, 11, and 12 are 0.211, 0.526, and 0.263 respectively. So, consequently, node 10 will be associated with 11 (already node 11 has been connected to node 7). Thus, node 10 would be connected to node 4 indirectly. Further, load assigned to DIs 4, 5, 7, 9, and 14 become 1.9, 0.6, 2.526, 0, and 1.166 respectively.

Therefore, none of the sensor nodes is assigned to the domain initial DI9 and the load assigned to DI5 is less than the MA threshold value. Thus, both domains need to be dropped out. It is required that nodes associated with the domains DI5 and DI9 should be associated with some other domain initials. DI9 contains a single element, 9 and DI5 contains two elements nodes 1 and 5. Thus, the set of nodes {1, 5, 9} needs to be dropped out. Similarly, this set of nodes will be connected to the respective DI.

5. EVALUATIVE ASSESSMENT

- In this paper, the modification of the proposed algorithm produced three distinct domains: {1, 2, 3, 4, 6}, {7, 10, 11, 12}, and {5, 9, 13, 14, 15}, with node 8 chosen as the Processing Element.
- In contrast, applying the FCM algorithm to general/wired networks, as described in [46], resulted in a different partitioning of the instance network into three domains: {1, 2, 3, 4, 5}, {6, 7, 10, 11, 12}, and {9, 13, 14, 15}.
- Both networks were structured with an equal number of domains and an identical number of nodes per domain, though the specific nodes within each domain varied.
- The loads for the wired networks were determined as $\min L(\text{wired})$, $\min L(\text{wired}) + 0.2$, and $\min L(\text{wired}) + 0.4$, where $\min L(\text{wired})$ represents the minimum load.
- The loads for the wireless networks were $\min L(\text{wireless})$, $\min L(\text{wireless}) + 0.374$, and $\min L(\text{wireless}) + 0.306$, with the minimum load for wireless networks denoted as $\min L(\text{wireless})$.
- In both cases, the domains maintained the same cardinality of 4, 5, and 5 nodes; however, the composition of nodes within each cluster differed between the two algorithms.

6. CONCLUSION

The research paper introduces the Adaptive Fuzzy c-Means (AFCM) algorithm to address the limitations of existing clustering methods like k-means, x-means, and Fuzzy c-Means (FCM) in multi-mobile agent itinerary planning (MIP). The AFCM algorithm enhances network clustering by effectively managing sensor nodes with equal membership values and ensuring balanced, non-overlapping domains. This improvement optimizes the efficiency of MIP systems, particularly under varying constraints. The algorithm demonstrated success in partitioning networks into well-balanced domains and suggested an appropriate number of mobile agents for optimized performance.

Future research can be focused on exploring the AFCM algorithm's performance under diverse network constraints and in larger-scale systems. Additionally, integrating AFCM with real-world MIP applications could further validate its effectiveness and scalability.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare. All the co-authors have seen and agree with the contents of the manuscript and there is no financial interest to report.

Each author have made substantial contributions to the conception or design of the work; or the acquisition, analysis, or interpretation of data.

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